

The Impacts and Contributions of Nigeria in The Promotion of Ecowas: A Critical Appraisal

Dada Samuel Olabode (Ph.D)

Department of Social Science Education, Bamidele Olumilua University of Education, Science and Technology, Ikere-Ekiti, Nigeria,
Email: dada.olabode@bouesti.edu.ng
Phone: 07032259033

Abstract

This paper discusses the role of Nigeria in the promotion of ECOWAS. Nigeria has not benefited much from the organization taken into consideration the large amount of money spent and human resources wasted by the country to support ECOWAS. The paper attempts to broadening the knowledge of the people about their membership of the organization. This study relied on the facts extracted from the library and works of previous writers on the concept. Historic analysis was equally explored. The paper highlights the formation of ECOWAS on bilateral and multilateral grounds. The objective of the ECOWAS was also discussed with respect to Nigeria's financial obligations and leadership role played. Role theory underpinned the study. The paper identified among others that if domestic political and economic problems in the country are realistically tackled the nation will experience political and economic growth. The paper concludes that there must be political will of neighbor members which is a basic element of integration in order to achieve much.

Keywords: bilateral, multilateral, foreign policy, sub-region, regional power and troops.

Introduction

Foreign policy connotes a course of action or set of principles by a nations government to define its relations with other countries or group of countries. A country's foreign policy also sets forth its positions on a wide range of international issues.

ECOWAS began operation in 1977, its member states are Benin, Burkina Faso, Cape Verde, Cote D'voire, The Gambia, Ghana, Guinea, Guinea Bissau, Liberia, Mali, Mauritania, Niger, Nigeria, Senegal, Sierra Leone and Togo. ECOWAS is administered through a secretariat which is based in Lagos, Nigeria (Akinyemi, Falegan and Aluko 1984). The Economic Community of West Africa States (ECOWAS; also known as CEDEAO in French and Portuguese) is a regional political and economic union of fifteen countries comprises an area of 5,114,162km'

(1,974,589sq mi) and have an estimated population of over 424.34 million. (ibid)

The foreign policy of nations evolves and develop over time and with regimes, fire by foreign international experience and series of domestic events. At independence, the Nigerian government under Balewa enunciated the foreign policy, principles and objectives of the newly independent nation. A desire to play the leadership role in Africa and to be the continent spokesperson in international affairs has been one of the main objectives of the Nigerian foreign policy. Hence, Nigeria has played a key role in the formation of the sub-region economic grouping known as Economic Community of West Africa States. (Akinyemi 1984)

This paper will discuss the background to the formation of ECOWAS, objectives of ECOWAS, motivation for Nigeria role in promotion of ECOWAS, The role theory, Nigeria role in the

promotion of ECOWAS, the implication for Nigeria and conclusion.

Background to the formation of Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS)

Since the early years of independence, Nigeria has played a key role in the formation of economic groupings in West Africa in particular and in the continent in general. These were made at two levels- bilateral and multilateral. In 1964, both the River Niger Basin Commission and the Chad Basin Commission were established at the initiative of Nigeria. It was the bilateral agreement between Nigeria and Togo in April, 1972, that paved the way for the formation of the ECOWAS in May, 1975 by the treaty of Lagos.

In 1972, a combination of circumstances made the promotion of the community an attraction ventures for Nigeria. The first was the recognition of Biafra by Ivory Coast during the civil war. It was realised that being in rapprochement with neighbour's countries was basic to Nigeria's national security if they are not to serve as platforms for the promotion of political instability (Olusanya and Akindele, 1986)

The second circumstance was Nigeria emergence as a regional power, partly because of the large revenue accruing to the country from the sale of crude oil. It was the crude oil revenue, which enabled Nigeria to prosecute the civil war and assist some of the most economically seriously affected West African States. For example, Benin received N1.8million for the construction of a 2kilometres high way linking Port Novo, Benin and Idi-iroko. Nigeria Jeunesses de la Revolution Democratique Africaine, one of the main political party in Guinea received N50,000 and Mali got N80,000 towards draught relief (ibid)

The desire to play the leadership role of a spokesperson in international affairs has been one of the main objectives of Nigeria foreign policy.

Even the modest leader such as the country's first Prime Minister, Sir Abubakar, believed that it was Nigeria and not Ghana that should speak for Africa. (Olajide Aluko, 1983)

Thirdly, there was the commitment by Nigeria political leaders to make the country the industrial centre of the continent of Africa. The establishment of an economic community in the region was perceived as part of the political-economic restructuring needed to enhance cooperation and collective self-reliance basic to redressing the problems of regional underdevelopment.

Also, Nigeria has sought to propel its West African neighbours through cooperation among them. More than any African country, Nigeria can unequivocally claim consistent interest in promoting the graduals integration of West Africa economics. Since independence the main tenets guiding Nigeria's relations with its neighbours are its aspirations for collective African economics, social and technological development that would ensure unity and stability. (Owosekun 1986). In addition to boasting the highest average regional AVOI score on the continent, Nigeria was in the vanguard of ensuring ECOWAS enjoys the highest visa-free reciprocity rate. The citizens of ECOWAS member states can enter 97% of all country destinations within ECOWAS visa-free, with the citizens of their host country doing likewise. It was made possible with the introduction of ECOWAS passport that enables their citizens to access other member nations. All these attempts were to promote healthy trade transactions and development among member countries.

Due to the traditional, almost umbilical, cultural, economic and political links between France and the Francophone, states were lukewarm and vary. By April 1972, Nigeria and Togo had set the tone by signing a treaty establishing the

nucleus of ECOWAS in Lagos on May, 27. By 1975, 15 West Africa states had signed with two of Nigeria closest neighbouring Cameroon and Chad conspicuously absent.

It is important to note that today Niger, Burkina Faso and Mali announced their withdrawal from the bloc. These countries had been suspended from ECOWAS due to military takeovers of their respective governments.

Objectives of ECOWAS

The aims of the community are to promote cooperation and development in all fields of industry, Transport, Telecommunication, Energy, Agriculture, Natural Resources, Commerce, Monetary and Financial question in social and cultural matters for the purpose of raising the standard of its over 200million people, of increasing and maintaining economic stability, of fostering closer relation among its members and of contributing to the progress and development of the African continent (Canteef, 1990). In the opinion of Agho 2020, he calculated ECOWAS population to be 180.8million in 1990. It was increased to 393.4million in 2019. The projected figure in 2043 is 765.1million people.

According to Owosekun (1980), the objectives of the ECOWAS was stated as follows:

(i) The elimination between the member states of custom and other charges of equivalent effect in respect of the importation and exportation of goods.

(ii) The abolition of quantitative and administrative restrictions on trade among member states

(iii) The establishment of a common custom tariff and a common commercial policy toward third world countries.

(iv) The abolition of the obstacles to the free movement of persons, services and capital between member states.

(v) The harmonization of the agricultural practices and the promotion of common projects in the member states notably in the field of marketing, research and agro-industrial enterprises.

(vi) The implementation of schemes for the joint development of Transport, Communication, Energy and other infrastructural facilities as well as the evolution and a common policy in these fields.

(vii) The harmonisation of economic and industrial policies of member states and the elimination of disparities in the level of development of member states.

(viii) The harmonisation required for the proper functioning of the community of the monetary policies of the member states.

(ix) The establishment of a fund for cooperation compensation and development.

(x) Such other activities calculated to further the aims of the community as the member state may from time to time undertake a common Article 2 in order to assist it in achieving these goals. ECOWAS has set up the following institutions:

(a) The authority of Heads of States and Government – the highest decision making organ of the community. It meets once in a year.

(b) The Council of Ministers – made up of two Ministers representing each member state. They meet twice a year and all its decisions are taken by consensus.

(c) The Executive Secretariat – headed by an Executive Secretary appointed by the authority. The Executive Secretary assisted by two Deputy Executive Secretary. He is responsible for the day to day administration and smooth functioning of the secretariat which have a staff of over 200. He is

the Chief Executive of the community and all his institution. The Executive Secretary is stationed in Lagos, Nigeria.

(d) The Tribunal of the community—Its role is to ensure observance of law and justice and principle of equity in the interpretation of the clauses of the treaty.

(e) The Defence Council.

(f) Technical and Specialised Commissions.

There are 5 of such commissions:

- The Trade, Customs, Immigration, Money and Payment Commission.
- The Industry, Agriculture and National Resources Commission.
- The Social and Cultural Commission.
- The Transport, Telecommunication and Energy Commission.
- The Administration and Finance Commission.

A fund for cooperation, compensation and development was established in 1976 based in Lome, Togo and a Managing Director headed it. The objectives are to:

- Provide compensation and other forms of assistance to member states, which have suffered losses as a result of trade liberalisation within the community. Or as a result of the location of community enterprises.
- To promote development projects in less developed member state of the community.
- To finance development activities of community interest, provide loans for projects and guarantee foreign investment in member states of the community.

A number of Technical and Social Institutions complete the original structure. They deal with specific issues and include:

- Committee of West African Central Banks
- Special Telecommunication Fund
- Energy Resource Development Fund
- Organisation of Trade Unions of West Africa
- West Africa Youth Association
- West Africa Women Association
- Federation of West Africa Association for the Advancement of handicapped persons.
- West Africa Clearing House
- Federation of West African Chamber of Commerce
- Federation of West African Manufactural Association
- West Africa Health Organization
- Youth and Sport Minister Conference and
- West Africa Football Union. (Akinyemi 1984)

Motivation for Nigeria 's Role in the Promotion of ECOWAS:

To keep Nigeria's role in ECOWAS and its bilateral relations with its immediate neighbours in proper perspective, one must be guided by variety of Economic, Cultural, Strategic external and Geographical considerations that have a crucial impact on its foreign policy.

The pre-eminent factor in that Nigeria is the largest country especially at the sub-regional level. Nigeria occupies 35% of the land area of West Africa with its over 200million inhabitants which is about 56% of ECOWAS countries population of 424.34million in 2023 and its GDP estimated at US\$633.1 billion was greater than the combined total for the 14 Francophone states. Also, Nigeria citizens are scattered in great numbers all over West Africa. (Ogwu in Dada 2024)

The Nigeria drive to establish a lasting framework for trade and economic cooperation with its neighbours was confirmed by the former

commissioner for external affairs. Joe Garba, when he stated that the maintenance of good relations with her neighbours was one of the cornerstone of Nigeria foreign policy (ibid, 94). In view of this objective Nigerian government have placed high priority on economic and development matters relevant to its neighbours in its diplomatic hierarchy.

On the multinational front, the remarkable success of the European Economic Community

(EEC) and The European Free Trade Association provide additional stimulus for revitalizing Nigeria's aspiration for economic cooperation in West Africa.

As leadership is important in any political system, it is very crucial when a group of countries embarked on a process of integration such as ECOWAS. Nigeria, no doubt, is one of the leading actors in the activities of ECOWAS. The various successive governments recognized this fact. In this line, Chief M.S. Adigun remarked in a policy statement at the ECOWAS secretariat that "Nigeria would continue to play active role in the affairs of ECOWAS because in it lies to a great extent our people and ability to liberate themselves from economic predicaments and socio- political instability (Olusanya and Akindele 1986; 131).

The role theory

Role theory refers to the cultural norms regarding psychology and interactional aspects of members of society, such as mother, father, son daughter and ground parents. The original originator of role theory is Ralph Linton in Sociology and George Herbert Mead in Social psychology.

Role theory operates under the key assumption that individual have various roles that they play in daily life (Biddle, 1986). These roles affect how the individual behaves and sees themselves and how the individual behaviour is perceived by others.

Role theory of leadership understands leadership with a group as a result of a process of differentiation by which group members achieve group aims faster and whereby they meet their individual needs. Hence leadership is considered as being a part of the problem-solving machinery of groups (Gibb,1959 p.103).

Nigeria as a leading nation of the regional block called ECOWAS, has a lot of roles to play, be it social, cultural, economic and political roles among the member states. Each member of the organization has their own roles to play towards the achievement of the aims and objectives of the organization.

Nigeria's Role in the Promotion of ECOWAS

Nigeria not only discharges her financial obligation to the community but also plays leadership roles in ECOWAS. Nigeria believes in the building of a regional institution as prerequisite for the establishment of a meaningful regional integration arrangement. Its annual contribution of 32.5% of the community budget, is paid regularly in order to ensure the effective operation of the community (ibid). Even when every member was owing the organization some money, a decision was made at Quagadougou submit in 1989 that every member should clear their areas. Nigeria as the founding father proceeded to clear her areas. (Contact1990;27). Hence, Nigeria ensures that her contribution was paid regularly both to the capital of the ECOWAS fund and in contribution to the regular budget of the ECOWAS secretariat.

Financial assistance has also usually been extended to the secretariat located in Lagos, Nigeria in times of crisis. For example, in June 1985, the federal government of Nigeria settled a some of N80,000 outstanding in respect of house rents for the community technocrats (Olusanya and Akindele 1986).

Nigeria contributed greatly to the program for the transport and communication projects. Nigerian federal government completed some highways. For example, the Lagos—Badagry—Contonou (Awesekun, 1986:204). So also is her effort in the construction of railway lines and highways from Nigeria to Republic of Niger in 2019/21 for political, economic, and strategic consideration by Nigerian government under former president M. Buhari. To complements its efforts, the government approved the establishment of Zaria Railway Training Institute (National Institute of Transport Technology) at estimated cost of \$10.3million(ibid).

Nigeria provide facilities to meet career training and for retraining of middle and top management personnel considered essential for maintenance, growth and survival of the government and that of the railway industry.

To ensure Nigerianization of large number of vacancies in the engineering field where there is great dependence of expatriates.

Nigeria provides for staff wastage on a planned basis.

In addition, was National College of Nigeria, situated at Oron, Cross Rivers State that became operational in 1979 to provide engineers in nautical training program to serve the need of Nigeria and other African countries.

River transportation on Benue and Niger rivers also serve as major international waters(ibid).

- (1) The federal government had given active support for the formation of such regional institutions as the West Africa Clearing House and ECOWAS Bank, which are vital to monetary cooperation and trade expansion in the region.

Bilateral steps have been taken to invest in some economic ventures of some member

states. Nigeria investments in iron mining in Benin, Uranium in the Republic of Niger, Cement and Sugar project in Benin and Petrol Chemicals in Senegal are very illustrative. To this, Hon. Abdul Karim Koroma, Minister of foreign affairs of Sierra –Leone in 1990 realized the role of Nigeria as he submitted “ Our iron mines have been moribund for sometime but now we are seeking to interest Nigeria in the revival of the industry. We also get our crude oil supply from Nigeria because the quality is eminently suitable for our refinery and also because the proximity of the source is very convenient for us” (Contact;1990)

Nigeria interventionist role in the Liberia and Serra-Leone civil wars within the ECOWAS organisation framework of the standing protocol relating to mutual assistance on Defence and in pursuance of her defined foreign policy. When all efforts at resolving Liberian crisis were to no avail, President Babangida during the 13th annual summit of Authority of Head of States and Government between 28th and 30th, May, 1990 in Banjul, Gambia proposed the setting up of a Community Standing Mediation Committee.

- (2) Consultation with warring factions didn't yield any positive fruit and there was need for a direr and forceful involvement which called for the decision to set up ECOWAS Monitoring Group (ECOMOG) in August, 1990 (Okoodi, 1992) ECOMOG was established for the purpose of peace keeping restoring law and order and ensuring that the cease-fire is respected.

According to Kunle Ajayi(in Dipo Kolawole 1998), Nigeria towering role in the ECOMOG manifest in the area of troop composition. At the peak of the war, ECOMOG strength was about 20,000 troop. Nigeria alone accounted for between 70-90% of the troops.

While it provides the bulk of the logistics needs, arms and ammunition. Nigerians were six out of the Seven field commanders of the force (ibid). Out of the 3,000 ECOMOG soldiers deployed in Sierra-Leone, 2,000 were Nigerians with a mandate to restore law and order and re-establish democracy by restoring Kabbah back to power (ibid). Besides, the vanguard (Vanguard, Lagos, May 12 1995;3) reported that over 4.0 Billion had been spent as at May 1995 on ECOMOG. The foreign Minister (Tom Ikimi) while attending a UN conference on assistance to Liberia indicated that \$3Billion has been spent so far on troops-ragging between 6,000 and 11,000 maintenances (Vanguard Lagos Oct. 29,1995 Pp. 1&2)

Nigeria role in promotion of ECOWAS can be understood from many perspectives as aforementioned. Due to her size and place in the region, she is the largest in the sub-region and economically better off. Citizens of Nigeria are also scattered in the countries of the sub-region. In addition, she has her investment in some of the countries to protect that is, her involvement is inspired in part by economic motives (Ajayi in Dipo Kolawole 1998;184).

Notwithstanding, there has not been adequate information system about employment opportunities in member states to cater for the issue of free movement. Also, the expulsion of illegal aliens mostly other ECOWAS citizens from Nigeria in 1983 and 1985 had done damage to the spirit of integration. The closure of the border has put an end to smuggling across the border and been portray Nigeria as a country which puts national interest before regional interest. (Olusanya and Akindele 1986;132) The continued closure of boarder in1984, 2016 by Buhari's government and recently in 2023 by Tinubu's administration. Most especially the

closure carried out as sanction against the Niger Republic in 2023 with the continued border closure between Benin Republic and Nigeria have lend to these challenges. (Dada, 2023). French influence in the region represents a major distraction to the coordination of the strategies of integration with the ECOWAS. French had been responding in the form of increased financial aid to the region.

Nigeria cannot exert itself significantly in certain issues where allegation of domination could damage. One of the criticisms of the treaty of Lagos is that Nigeria is apt to dominate the other countries by reason of its population and wealth. The fear of domination is still problematic in the community. Both Senegal and Ivory Coast have from time to time expressed their reservations about the growing influence and role of Nigeria in the region.

Implication for Nigeria

Though the role of Nigeria in the promotion of ECOWAS was a matter of her foreign policy as posited by Babangida and Abacha (Okoosi1997 in Kolawole 1998;187). The question is that at what cost and where exactly should the line be drawn on the extend of Nigeria foreign policy. For example, Nigeria 's involvement in Liberia has not added to the nation's socio-economic wellbeing in anyway. Nigeria lost men, money and materials expend without the possibility of any reimbursement. African Concord of January1992 recorded that a total of 58 Nigeria soldiers had died in the course of the operation due to both violent and non-violent causes (Okoosi 1997;34).

Nwolise, in a paper presented to the ASUU Conference on the state of the nation in 1994, lamented that the country is yet to use her foreign policy as a strategic instrument of economic development in practice and that it is high time the country recognized the relevance

of this action (ibid). According to a former External Affairs Minister, the country foreign policy has been geared towards the pursuit of political goals to the neglect of economic development especially in its role in ECOMOG.

Besides, the role of Nigeria in the promotion of ECOWAS pose a great challenge to her to look inward to solve her domestic problems which range from political instability, prolonged marginalization, economic instability, human rights issues and many others.

Nigeria in most cases is made the Chairman of the regional organization and champions the course of the organization. The irony of it all is that Nigerian who poses to be a messiah to sub-region states has its internal challenges to be addressed. It all amount to power politics. Discussant held the view that Nigeria gains nothing but gained praise, glory, and attention as she initiated and carried out the business of ECOMOG like her own personal affairs. This manifested in 2023 when President Tinubu on assumption of office without a clear knowledge of the operations of ECOWAS, at his first time of presiding over the body to address Niger issue, he quickly suspended the member nation and other sanctions followed with the support of others. The result was the disintegration carried out by other nations that were in line with Niger

Conclusion

The role of Nigeria in the promotion of ECOWAS is a direction if the domestic political and economic problems in the country are realistically tackled, the nation will experience political stability and economic growth.

To keep its leadership pace in the ECOWAS. Nigeria should set the example in the home politics. The state of the nation 's political and economic stability will earn her more respect in the neighbouring country.

Besides, there must be the political will of neighbouring members, which is a basic element of integration. Also there should be sustained commitment to the ECOWAS at the highest level of government based on the understanding of sustained benefits that could accrue to the region political support by social groups and mass support by the people by one country towards those of others without suspicion will reflect on the process of integration.

REFERENCES

- Akinyemi, Falegan and Aluko (2015). "Readings and Documents on ECOWAS": Nigeria Institute of international Affairs. P.113
- Antonia T. Okoosi (1997). "Global Versus Regional peace-keeping": Nigeria Institute of Social & Economic Research (NISER) P 21-36
- Biddle B.J. (1986) Recent development in Role Theory. *Annual Review Sociology*. 12, 67-92. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annuerv.so.12.080186.0000435>
- Dada S.O. (2023). *Power and Politics in Nigeria*. Ado. Omobala Publishers.
- Kolawole D (2020). *Issues in Nigeria Government and Politics* P. 180-186.
- Olajide Aluko (2019) *Nigeria Foreign Policy: Alternatives, Perceptions and Projections*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Olusanya, G.G & Akindele, R.A (1986). *Nigeria's External Relations*. 8Unuversity Press Limited p, 127-136

-
- Okoosi, A.T. (1997). Global versus Regional Peace Keeping: Nigeria Institute of Social & Economic Research (NISER) P. 31-36
- Owosekun, A.A. (1986). “Towards and African Economic Community” Nigeria Institute of Social & Economic Research (NISER) P. 113-211
- Timothy Shaw and Olajide Aluko (2021). Nigeria Foreign Policy, alternative perspectives projection; Ibadan Macmillan Press Ltd. P. 192-193
- U. Joy Ogwu (1986) Nigeria Foreign Policy: Alternatives Futures. Lagos. Nigeria Institute of International Affairs in co-operation with Macmillan Nigeria Publishers
- Tom Ikimi (1995). “Nigeria Expenditure on ECOMOG”, Vanguard, Lagos. May, 12. P 3
- Tom Ikimi (1995). “Resistance to Liberia”. Vanguard , Lagos, Oct, 29. P 2-3